

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE EFFECT OF CORONAVIRUS (COVID-19) IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY IN MOLDOVA

Luca T.

*PhD student, specialty Marketing and Logistics,
State University of Moldova, Chisinau*

Abstract

The study aims to measure the impact of the occurrence of corona virus on the tourism industry in the Republic of Moldova. The research findings show that the tourism industry managed to adapt to the new reality, emphasizing the safety of tourists, creativity and originality in the creation and promotion of tourist offers. Due to this virus threat, the global tourists have cancelled their programs to visit Moldova and the moldovan tourists are banned to visit overseas nations. The rapid spread of the Corona virus in the world has stopped the normal life of the people. This fear has impacted the tourism industry of the country domestically and internationally. This has affected the economy of the country to a large extent. The intensification of the Corona virus is being thought to cause a long term impact on the tourism industry of the Republic of Moldova.

Keywords: Safe tourism, coronavirus, impact one the Moldavian tourism industry, sustainability.

Tourism plays an important role in the economy of the countries of the world due to its potential its economic and employment impact, as well as its implications social and environmental. Tourism, in its various forms, has experienced development and diversification accentuated in the last decades so that, at the beginning of the 21st century, it is considered as one of the most dynamic fields of current civilization. Argument it is mainly represented by the permanent transformation, as a result of the adaptation of the phenomenon tourism to the global economic requirements of globalization and sustainable development a the service sector.

Unfortunately, the pandemic caused by the Covid-19 virus hit the branch hard tourism, generating a decrease of approx. 75-80%, in 2020 compared to 2019, of international arrivals and a considerable decrease in revenues from the activity touristic [2].

As the effects of COVID-19 began to be felt all over the world, the impact on the HORECA industry became inevitable. The decisions taken to close hotels,

restaurants, theme parks, cinemas led to the disruption of an entire ecosystem. Many interconnected industries have started looking for solutions to adapt to a completely new paradigm.

Restriction of interstate traffic imposed by national authorities of Moldova, as well as other countries, has seriously affected tourism. The first received blow was due to the cancellation of previously made reservations. In the absolute majority of cases, these bookings represented over 60% of the turnover. Thus, travel agencies lost around 52 million lei in orders, airlines 40 million lei, hotels 29.5 million lei, and event organizers 2.5 million lei.

Moldova is a tourist destination of major interest for citizens of other countries, the number of foreign visitors being constantly increasing (table no. 1). In 2019, the Republic of Moldova was visited by 4.6 million foreign citizens, with 0.3 million people more than in 2018, which is a 6.2% increase. Compared to 2013, the number of visitors to our country practically doubled (94.9% increase, average annual rate + 12%) [4].

Table 1.

Statistical data regarding the crossing of the state border by foreign citizens in the years 2013-2020, entries, mln. people.

Year	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2019 compared to 2013	2020 compared to 2013
Total mln. people, in percentage compared to the previous year	2,36	2,23	2,86	3,40	3,90	4,33	4,60	1,39	+2,24 mln people	-0,94 mln. people
		-6%	+14,8%	+18,8%	+14,7%	+11,7%	+6,2%	70%	+94,9%	-41%

Surse: Made by the author based on the source [4].

In 2019, in the 267 hotels or other accommodation establishment, with a capacity of 24.5 thousand rooms, 374.8 thousand people were accommodated,

with 10.2 thousand people more than in 2018, which is an increase of 2.8% (tables no. 2).

Table 2.

**The number of tourists staying in the hotels or other accommodation establishment
in 2013 – 2020 years, thousands of people**

Years	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Foreign tourists	95,6	93,9	94,4	121,3	145,2	160,2	174,0	28,7
In percentage compared to the previous year		-2,0 %	+0,5%	+28,5%	+19,6%	+10,4%	+10,9%	-83,5%
Local tourists	175,9	189,1	184,5	184,9	192,0	204,4	200,7	61,6
In percentage compared to the previous year		+7,5%	-2,5%	+0,3%	+3,8%	+6,4%	-1,8%	-69,3%
Total number tourists	271,5	283,0	278,9	306,3	337,2	364,6	374,8	90,3
In percentage compared to the previous year		+4,2%	-1,5%	+9,8%	+10,0%	+8,1%	+2,8%	-75,9%

Surse: Made by the author based on the source [4].

Unfortunately, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the number of tourists staying in the hotels or other accommodation establishment in 2020 decreased considerably, being in decrease by approx. 76% compared to 2019.

Compared to 2013, the total number of tourists staying in the hotels or other accommodation establishment decreased by approx. 181 thousand people, which is a decrease of approx 67%, the most important decrease being seen in the number of foreign tourists – approx 70%.

Travel restrictions applied by all countries of the world for the purpose of prevention the spread of the Covid-19 virus has dramatically affected the activity of

travel agencies, in especially with reference to out-bound tourism, which, compared to 2013, recorded a decrease of approx. 54%. The number of tourists in the area has also decreased by almost 2 times receiving tourism (6.2 thousand in 2020 compared to 13.2 thousand people in 2013).

Also in 2020, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the volume of receipts from the activity of travel agencies decreased by 1.7 billion lei compared to 2019, which is a decrease of approx. 69%.

The volume of receipts in 2020, compared to 2013, decreased by 0.22 billion lei, which is a decrease of about 22%.

Table 4.

**The volume of receipts from the activity of travel agencies
(tour operators and travel agencies) in 2013, 2018-2020.**

Year	2013	2018	2019	2020	2019 comparatively with 2013	2020 comparatively with 2013
Total, billion lei, In percentage compared to the previous year	1,0	1,8 -5,3%	2,5 +38,9%	0,78 -68,8%	+1,5 billion lei +250%	-0,22 billion lei -22%

Surse: Made by the author based on the source [4].

It is important to note that travel restrictions have also affected foreign tourism. According to estimates, the annual cost of vacations over border of Moldova, it amounts to approximately 150 million Euros. Domestic tourism is not a viable alternative. Even if the our compatriots "rediscover Moldova", accommodation expenses are most often avoided, given that the short distances allow occasional tourists to return home [2].

The crisis has revealed the need to rethink the structure of tourism economies to improve competitiveness and build resilience. To that end, the sector could:

✓ Adopt new policy frameworks, more conducive for a sound and resilient business environment;

✓ Support the development of tourism infrastructure and quality services that enable the development of other related sectors and facilitate investment for local MSMEs;

✓ Provide alternative income sources for tourism-dependent communities to build crisis resilience;

✓ Establish an inclusive model – productive linkages between the tourism sector and the rest of the economy, especially transport and trade sectors through various goods and services;

✓ Diversify markets, tourists products and address seasonality and promote all-year round demand;

✓ Improve the interlinkages between enhanced transport connectivity and tourism and strengthen resilient and sustainable transport infrastructures as an enabling factor to steer the tourism sector on a more sustainable and inclusive path;

✓ Promote safe domestic and regional tourism, where possible;

This crisis offers an unprecedented opportunity to transform the relationship between the tourism sector and nature and so contribute more absolutely to the Sustainable Development Goals.

Also the digitalization and innovative solutions provide a unique opportunity to scale up operational procedures that make travel safe and seamless while mitigating the possible impact of new protocols in terms of increased waste generation, water and energy use. Electronic check-in at hotels, touchless border control and airline boarding can advance safety and security while minimizing waste. Additionally, necessary health and safety protocols may lead to more waste, including masks, gloves, gowns, food packaging, and other disposable protective equipment. There may also

be a rise in water consumption, putting additional pressure on water scarcity and waste management [5].

In conclusion

Tourism, one of the most dynamic and most job intensive sectors of our times, has been one of the hardest hit by the current crisis. Millions of livelihoods are at stake and need to be supported. As countries gradually lift travel restrictions and tourism slowly restarts in many parts of the world, health must continue to be a priority and coordinated health protocols that protect workers, communities and travelers while supporting companies and workers must be firmly in place. International cooperation needs to be stepped up, especially around travel restrictions and border management, to ensure support to livelihoods and economies with responsibility and sense of solidarity. Efforts such as that initiated only a few weeks after the outbreak, by the national authorities, the Investment Agency together with the National Authority for Inbound and Domestic Tourism in Moldova, to boost the recovery of the tourism sector along the three pillars of the COVID19. Tourism recovery technical and economic assistance package, with a focus on preserving human capital as well as adapting and strengthening inclusion, must be maintained and upscaled.

The crisis is also an opportunity to rethink the tourism sector and its contribution to the sustainable development goals, an opportunity to work towards a more sustainable, inclusive and resilient tourism. Only through collective action and international cooperation

will we be able to transform tourism, advance its contribution and its shift towards an inclusive and carbon neutral sector that harnesses innovation and digitalization, embraces local values and communities and creates decent job opportunities for all, leaving no one behind.

References

1. How COVID-19 is changing the world: a statistical perspective Volume II, CCSA, 2020, 77 pg, https://unstats.un.org/unsd/ccsa/documents/covid19-report-ccsa_vol2.pdf
2. Matricea Covid, Raport elaborat de Consiliul Economic pe lângă Prim-Ministru, 106 pg, <https://consecn.gov.md/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/Studiul-de-Impact-al-Pandemie-COVID-19-asupra-sectoarelor-economice-%C8%99i-Matricea-cu-politici.pdf>
3. Policy Brief: COVID-19 and Transforming Tourism, United Nations, august 2020, 27 pg., <https://webunwto.s3.eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/2020-08/SG-Policy-Brief-on-COVID-and-Tourism.pdf>
4. Raport privind realizarea în anii 2014-2020 a Strategiei de dezvoltare a turismului ”Turism 2020”, 78 pag, Chişinău 2021, https://me.gov.md/sites/default/files/raport_sdt_turism_2020.pdf
5. UNWTO, “Healing Solutions for Tourism Challenge”, April 2019, available at <https://www.unwto.org/healing-solutions-tourism-challenge>